

METHODS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN FINLAND

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Annotatsiya: *This article examines the education system in Finland, which is widely considered one of the most effective in the world. It highlights key features such as free access to education, equal opportunities for all students, and modern teaching methods that focus on understanding rather than memorization. The paper also discusses the important role of highly qualified teachers and the supportive learning environment in Finnish schools. In addition, it analyzes the main advantages of the system in comparison with other countries. The article concludes that Finland's student-centered approach plays a key role in its educational success.*

Keywords: *Finnish education system, teaching method, school, quality, free education, compulsory education.*

Introduction: Education plays crucial role in people's life for development and society. It helps person become truly complete human being. Obviously, different countries have different approaches to education, but some of them are more successful than others. In recent years, many researchers and experts have paid attention to the quality of education around the world. One of the countries that is often considered to have one of the best education systems is Finland. This is because Finland focuses not only on academic results but also on students' well-being and equal opportunities. This article will explain the main features of the Finnish education system, its advantages, and the reasons why it is so effective, if we compare with others.

METHODS

Education system in Finland: Finland is renowned because of high quality system, including free access to schooling, same opportunities for students are disabled and healthy. Education from pre-primary to higher education is absolutely free for students. All things like books, learning materials, lunches, even computer or laptops are given and paid by government. Excursions, museums, and any extracurricular activities are free. Every year these schools are publicly funded and they never take any tuition fees from parents. Collecting money from parents for any purpose is prohibited. Besides, if students live within 2 km of the school, they are provided with free school buses^[3].

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Moreover, children in Finland start school at the age of 7 and the grades are from 1 to 9. However, compulsory education now extends until the age 18, requiring students to complete upper-secondary education. The Finnish education system consists of:

- Early childhood education and care which is provided for children before compulsory education begins;
- Pre-primary education which is provided for children in the year preceding the beginning of compulsory education;
- Nine-year basic education (comprehensive school), which is compulsory;
- Upper secondary education, which is either general upper secondary education or vocational education and training;
- Higher education provided by universities and universities of applied sciences;
- Furthermore, adult education is available at all levels^[2].

One important factor is that, the largest school has 960 students, the smallest one has only 11. All schools are equipped with exactly the same equipment, have the same facilities, and even are funded the same. Almost all schools are state schools, but there are dozens of private school^[3]. In addition, there is no any tests or exams during children's study. Only one standarts exam is taken, when they are 16 years old and before graduating secondary school. In Finland, it is considered that, children should have much time with their family at home, instead of doing lots of homework. That is why, homework is given for a short period of time.

Another important feature is that, the grading system is 10-point. However, students are not graded until grade 3. After grade 3, students are graded on a 10-point system. There is no reprimand or punishment for low grades. Grades are considered only as a motivational tool^[1].

The role of teachers: Teachers are more educated and highly respected in society. Most teachers are required to have a master's degree, which ensures a high level of professionalism before entering the school. The average monthly salary of teachers is €3,500. There is no fixed teaching program, the teacher decides in what style and based on what textbook to teach.

RESULTS

One of the main advantages of the education system in Finland is the low level of stress among students compared to many other countries. In countries like South Korea and Japan, students often experience high pressure because of frequent exams and heavy workloads. However, in Finland, students have fewer tests and less homework, which helps them enjoy learning. During class, students can sit at their own discretion - at a desk, sofa, carpet, or floor. Despite of relaxed environment, students achieve good academic results.

Furthermore, Finnish schools focus more on understanding and creativity, while many other countries focus mainly on memorization. This helps students develop critical thinking skills, which are important in real life. Additionally, it is not appropriate to teach one subject more deeply than another. For example, mathematics is not considered more important there than art. On the contrary, the only reason for creating separate classes for gifted children may be their inclination towards fine arts, music, and sports.

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CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the education system in Finland is widely recognized as one of the most successful in the world. This is mainly because it focuses on equality, quality, and student well-being rather than only academic competition. Free education, effective teaching methods, and highly qualified teachers all contribute to its success. In addition, the low level of stress and supportive learning environment help students achieve better results and enjoy their studies. Overall, Finland shows that a balanced and student-centered approach can lead to strong outcomes. Other countries can learn valuable lessons from Finland's approach to education and use them to improve their own systems.

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